

Fabrication of Polyamide 6-based CFRP with Water Resistance via T-RTM Process and Fluorinated Polydopamine Coating

Seung Mo Son^a, Minjung Kim^b, Jung Jae Yoo^a,
Min Seong Kim^b, Byeong-Su Kim^{b+}, Dong Gi Seong^{a,c+}

^A School of Chemical Engineering, Pusan National University, Republic of Korea

^B Department of Chemistry, Yonsei University, Republic of Korea

^C Department of Polymer Science and Engineering, Pusan National University, Republic of Korea

E-mail : ssm6568@pusan.ac.kr, bskim19@yonsei.ac.kr, dgseong@pusan.ac.kr

Homepage : composite.pusan.ac.kr

INDEX

Introduction

- PA 6-based CFRTP

Experiment

- T-RTM process
- Polydopamine chemistry

Result and discussion

- Surface elements analysis
- Surface morphology analysis
- Water resistance test
- Anti-icing test

Conclusion

Introduction : Polyamide 6 (PA 6)-based Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic (CFRTP)

Sustainable structural material owing to lightweight property and recyclability

<https://steamdaily.com/top-ten-awesome-uses-of-carbon-fibre-2/>

Advantages of PA 6-based CFRTP (compared to steel)

- Lightweight and anti-corrosion
- Superior specific strength and elasticity
- Short processing time (heating and cooling)

Advantages of PA 6-based CFRTP (compared to CFRP)

- High impact resistance
- Weldability and recyclability
- Low adhesion to mold and long shelf life

[Limitations for industrial and exterior application]

- ① **High melt viscosity of PA 6** : difficult to impregnate the resin into to fiber
- ② **Water absorption and high surface energy** : deterioration of mechanical properties

Concept 1 - T-RTM process : Liquid Molding Process for PA 6-based CFRTP

Integrated reactive process of mixing, injection, impregnation, and polymerization

Thermoplastic reactive resin transfer molding

- Tank 1 : monomer & activator
- Tank 2 : monomer & Grignard catalyst
- Anionic polymerization occurs in the preform

T-RTM's advantages

- Low processing temperature (150 °C)
- Low resin viscosity (0.01 Pa·s)
- Inexpensive material cost (ϵ -caprolactam)

Extremely low viscosity of resin : 1/100 of epoxy, 1/160,000 of PA 6

Advantageous process for large production of PA 6-based CFRTP

Concept 2 - Polydopamine Chemistry : Mussel-inspired Surface Treatment

Coating method with strong adhesive force by covalent and noncovalent interactions

<https://www.snexplores.org/article/mimicking-mussels-muscle-for-underwater-superglue-better-stitches>

Polydopamine (PDA) coating

- Robust and reliable surface treatment
- Suitable for large and complex shaped products
- Spherical aggregation (Cassie-Baxter state)

Fluorinated Polydopamine (f-PDA) coating

- Michael type addition reaction (click chemistry)
- Low surface energy and wettability
- Anti-fouling and water resistance performance

➔ Overcome the disadvantages of PA 6-based CFRT by T-RTM and f-PDA

Result and discussion : Surface Element Analysis of f-PDA : XPS and EDS

PDA was modified with fluoroalkyl chain by Michael-type addition reaction

f-PDA surface consisted of C (67.4 at%), O (20.6 at%), N (6.5 at%), and F (4.9 at%)

Fluorine's low surface energy : hydrophobicity and low wettability

Result and discussion : Surface Morphology Analysis of f-PDA : AFM and SEM

PDA's roughness was maintained in the f-PDA : Cassie-Baxter state

Result and discussion : Water Resistance and Durability Test of f-PDA-CFRTP

Chemical, thermal, and mechanical stability of f-PDA coating

f-PDA-CFRTP is durable enough to be applied as exterior materials

Result and Discussion : Water Absorption and Void Contents after Hydrolysis

Water absorption was reduced by 42% for 30 days by introduction of f-PDA

- CFRTTP → 60 °C D.I water for 30 days : Fickian diffusion behavior
→ amorphous region of PA 6 & interface of fiber and matrix
- PDA coating → physically barrier effect
- f-PDA coating → barrier effect + low wettability & hydrophobicity

Result and discussion : Mechanical Properties of f-PDA-CFRTP : ILSS and Flexural Test

Mechanical properties of composites at dry and wet states

Flexural strength : matrix-based property : **improved 31%**

ILSS : interfacial bonding between matrix and fiber : **improved 16%**

➔ **Deterioration of mechanical properties by water was alleviated by f-PDA**

Result and discussion : Anti-Icing Test f-PDA-CFRTP : Surface Energy Reduction

Surface energy was reduced by 49% : anti-icing, anti-fouling, and hydrophobicity

Substrates	Contact angles (°)		Surface energies (dyne/cm ²)		
	θ_{water}	$\theta_{\text{diiodomethane}}$	γ^D	γ^P	γ
CFRTP	64.4	30.0	37.1	10.7	47.8
PDA-CFRTP	73.2	32.4	38.3	6.1	44.4
f-PDA-CFRTP	90.1	69.6	19.8	4.6	24.4

① Chemical term : **surface energy** was reduced 49% (fluorine effect)

② Physical term : **friction between solid and liquid droplet** (PDA effect)

Conclusion : T-RTM and f-PDA Coating for PA 6-based CFRTP

Applying PA 6-based CFRTP as various external component in humid environments

Eco-friendly thermoplastic composite
by T-RTM process

- 1/160,000 of viscosity

Water absorption and surface energy

- f-PDA coating

- Water absorption was reduced by 42%

- Surface energy was reduced by 49%

Thank you for your attention

Composites Science and Technology 238 (2023) 110048

Fabrication of carbon fiber/polyamide 6 composites with water resistance and anti-icing performance using a superhydrophobic fluorinated-polydopamine coating

Seung Mo Son^{a,1}, Minjung Kim^{b,1}, Jung Jae Yoo^a, Min Seong Kim^b, Byeong-Su Kim^{b,*}, Dong Gi Seong^{a,c,*}

^a School of Chemical Engineering, Pusan National University, Busandaehak-ro 63beon-gil 2, Geumjeong-gu, Busan, 46241, Republic of Korea

^b Department of Chemistry, Yonsei University, Seoul, 03722, Republic of Korea

^c Department of Polymer Science and Engineering, Pusan National University, Busandaehak-ro 63beon-gil 2, Geumjeong-gu, Busan, 46241, Republic of Korea

<Advisor>

<Prof. Dong Gi Seong>
Pusan National Univ.

<Prof. Byeong-Su Kim>
Yonsei Univ.

<Co-worker>

- Minjung Kim (Yonsei Univ.)
- Jung Jae Yoo (Pusan national Univ.)
- Min Seong Kim (Yonsei Univ.)

<Acknowledgements>

- This research was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by Ministry of Science and ICT (2022M3H4A1A04076372 and 2021R1A2C3004978).

Polymer Composite Laboratory, Pusan National University, Busan, Republic of Korea

E-mail : ssm6568@pusan.ac.kr, bskim19@yonsei.ac.kr, dgseong@pusan.ac.kr

Homepage : composite.pusan.ac.kr

Fabrication of Polyamide 6-based CFRP with Water Resistance
via T-RTM process and Fluorinated Polydopamine Coating

Seung Mo Son

Polymer Composite Laboratory, Pusan National University, Busan, Republic of Korea

Homepage : www.composite.pusan.ac.kr

E-mail : ssm6568@pusan.ac.kr

Supporting information

Anti-icing test

Supporting information

AFM data (amplitude error, phase), Cassie-Baxter state

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cassie%27s_law

Supporting information

Owens-Wendt equation, water absorption, and diffusion coefficient of water

$$\gamma_{SL} = \gamma_{SG} + \gamma_{LG} - 2(\gamma_{SG}^d \cdot \gamma_{LG}^d)^{1/2} - 2(\gamma_{SG}^p \cdot \gamma_{LG}^p)^{1/2},$$

$$\gamma_{LG}(1 + \cos \theta) = 2(\gamma_{SG}^d \cdot \gamma_{LG}^d)^{1/2} + 2(\gamma_{SG}^p \cdot \gamma_{LG}^p)^{1/2},$$

$$\gamma_{SG} = \gamma_{SG}^d + \gamma_{SG}^p,$$

$$\text{Water absorption (\%)} = \frac{W_{wet} - W_{dry}}{W_{dry}} \times 100$$

$$D_{water} = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_m} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2$$

Y. Ma, S. Jin, T. Yokozeki, M. Ueda, Y. Yang, E.A. Elbadry, H. Hamada, T. Sugahara, Effect of hot water on the mechanical performance of unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced nylon 6 composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 200 (2020), 108426, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2020.108426>.

Supporting information

Color change and thickness optimization (ellipsometry)

Bare Si wafer

PDA-coated surface

(a)

(b)

